

Identification of maintainers and restorers for two cytoplasmic-genetic male sterile rice lines

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To identify maintainers and restorers for CMS lines V20 A and Shan 97 A, we evaluated pollen sterility of florets located in the upper third part of the panicle before dehiscence, florets stored at 2-11°C, and their pollen grains stained with IKI.

Maintainers and restorers^a for V20 A and Zhen Shan 97 A CMS lines at National Research Center, Palmira, Colombia.

Male parent ^a	V20 A	Zhen Shan 97 A
Fortuna blanco	M	M
Fortuna morado	M	M
Inamono	M	M
Taipei 309	M	M
Cacao Pelao	M	M
Taichung 176	M	M
IRAT 13	M	M
IRAT 12	M	M
Moroberekan	M	M
Monolaya	M	M
Miramono	M	M
Palawan	M	M
Suakoko	M	M
IRAT121	M	M
IRAT124	M	M
IRAT120	M	M
IRAT122	M	PR
Colombia 1	M	PR
Rexoro	M	M
Costa Rica	PR	M
Canilla	PR	M
L-5685	PR	PR
Monorecao	PR	PR
Llanero 501	PR	PR
Tapuripa	PR	PR
Blue-Bonnet 50	PR	PR
Araure	PR	PR
Metelapuya	PR	PR
Rustic	PR	PR
Tadukan	PR	PR
Cica 7	PR	PR
Cica 4	PR	PR
L-17388	PR	R
IR262	PR	PR
Metica 1	PR	R
Oryzica 1	PR	PR
Cica 9	PR	PR
Chianung Sen Yu 23	R	PR
IR22	R	R
Campeche A 80	R	R
L-11972	R	R
Cica 8	R	PR

^aM = maintainer, PR = partial restorer, R = restorer.

Hybrids were obtained from two CMS lines crossed with 42 standard native varieties and elite breeding lines with different growth durations.

Hybrids were transplanted in rows of 16 plants each, spaced 0.30 × 0.30 m. Eight plants, three panicles per plant, and three flowers per panicle were evaluated for sterility in the fields.

Male parents of the F₁ that showed 90-100% pollen sterility were designated maintainers. Male parents showing 21-89% pollen sterility were designated partial restorers. Male parents showing 0-20% pollen sterility were designated restorers. Maintainers were more frequent than restorers (see table). ■

Yield potential

Ratooning ability of some rice cultivars and hybrids

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We assessed ratooning yield on the basis of ratooning ability and a ratoon vigor scale. Rice genotypes Bhavani, MDU3,

IET6262, IET6709, IET7552, and IET9239 and their 30 hybrids developed on diallel crosses were planted in two rows of 10 plants each at 20- × 10-cm spacing in a randomized block design replicated three times. Recommended practices were followed for both main and ratoon crops.

The main crop was cut 20 cm from the ground at physiological maturity and allowed to ratoon. Ten randomly selected plants of each parent and hybrid from each replication were used to measure regenerated tillers and ratoon yield and to estimate ratooning ability and ratoon vigor.

Ratooning ability was assessed as number of ratoon tillers regenerated from stubble. Ratoon vigor was recorded as 1 = ratoon very vigorous (basal + nodal ratoons); 5 = ratoon normal or intermediate (only basal ratoons); and 9 = ratoon very weak or few (no counting).

A composite ratooning rating was estimated:

Ratooning rating = (1 - (0.1 ratoon vigor) × (av no. ratoon tillers/plant))

All parents except MDU3 and IET9239 showed high number of regenerated tillers. The parents IET6709, IET7552, and Bhavani recorded ratoon

Ratooning ability and yield of parents and hybrids.^a Madurai, India, 1988.

Parent or cross	Regenerated tillers (no./plant)	Ratoon vigor scale	Ratoon rating	Ratoon yield (g/10 plants)
Bhavani	8.7	1	7.8	14.4
MDU3	7.5	5	3.7	12.3
IET6262	8.9	5	4.5	12.8
IET6709	10.0	1	9.0	13.6
IET7552	9.1	1	8.2	15.1
IET9239	6.4	5	3.2	11.7
Bhavani/MDU3	9.1 (8.7)	1 (1)	8.2 (7.8)	14.5 (12.5)
Bhavani/IET6262	12.3 (10.8)	1 (1)	11.1 (9.7)	16.1 (13.2)
Bhavani/IET7552	10.1 (11.4)	1 (1)	9.1 (10.3)	14.9 (16.3)
Bhavani/IET6709	11.0 (12.7)	1 (1)	9.9 (11.5)	15.4 (15.1)
Bhavani/IET9239	8.5 (8.1)	1 (1)	7.6 (7.7)	14.3 (12.8)
MDU3/IET6262	10.4 (12.3)	5 (5)	5.2 (6.2)	12.8 (13.5)
MDU3/IET6709	9.8 (11.8)	1 (1)	8.8 (10.3)	13.1 (13.7)
MDU3/IET7552	8.7 (10.4)	5 (1)	4.3 (9.4)	12.4 (15.0)
MDU3/IET9239	8.9 (7.5)	5 (5)	4.4 (3.8)	12.5 (11.9)
IET6262/IET6709	13.1 (13.2)	1 (1)	11.8 (11.9)	14.4 (15.2)
IET6262/IET7552	10.4 (12.4)	1 (1)	9.4 (11.1)	13.0 (15.1)
IET6262/IET9239	10.1 (9.3)	5 (5)	5.1 (4.7)	12.8 (12.5)
IET6709/IET7552	15.3 (14.3)	1 (1)	13.8 (12.8)	15.2 (16.8)
IET6709/IET9239	10.2 (9.3)	1 (1)	9.2 (8.4)	13.5 (12.6)
IET7552/IET9239	10.8 (7.9)	1 (5)	9.7 (4.0)	15.9 (12.0)
Mean: Parent	8.4			13.3
Hybrids	10.6			14.0
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.8			0.8

^a Figures in the parentheses are for the reciprocal cross.